

Rehabilitation of Severely Worn Dentition In Maxillary Arch With Fixed and Removable Prosthesis .

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Abstract

Rehabilitation of a patient with severely worn dentition after restoring the vertical dimension is a complex procedure and assessment of the vertical dimension is an important aspect in these cases. It requires the prosthodontist's expertise in preserving the integrity of the oral structures. This case report describes a 65-year-old male, who complained of difficulty in mastication and unpleasant appearance due to loss of maxillary posterior tooth support, severe wear of dentition in maxillary anterior region, and the reduction of the occlusal vertical dimension. Articulation of study casts and a diagnostic wax-up was done to provide important information for the evaluation of treatment options. Alteration of the VDO should be conservative and should not be changed without careful consideration. As there was clinical evaluation of reduced VDO, rehabilitation of maxillary arch at increased VDO with fixed and removable prosthesis according to the patient's choice of treatment plan

Keywords: Tooth wear, Vertical dimension of occlusion,

Introduction

Over a patient's lifetime, the occlusal surfaces of their teeth will naturally gradually wear down. However, pulpal pathology, occlusal disharmony, impaired function, and esthetic disfigurement can be brought on by excessive occlusal wear¹.

Depending on the factors that causes it, tooth wear can be classified as erosion, abrasion, or attrition and leads to an alteration of the vertical dimension of occlusion (VDO). In certain cases, tooth eruption and alveolar bone growth often maintain the vertical dimension of occlusion (VDO). Wearing teeth causes the alveolar bone to adapt to compensate for lost tooth structure to preserve the VDO^{2,3}. Therefore, VDO should be conservative and should not be changed without a careful approach³. Especially, increasing the VDO in bruxers puts a severe overload on the teeth and often destroys the restorations or teeth themselves. However, the rehabilitation of the severely worn dentition is challenging when the space for restoration is not sufficient.

Management of worn dentition using fixed or removable prostheses is complex and among the most challenging cases to restore. A thorough treatment plan is necessary for every case, and the assessment of the vertical dimension is crucial for management of such cases. Articulated study casts and diagnostic wax-up can provide important information which is helpful for the evaluation of treatment options. Tolerance of changes to vertical dimension of occlusion is

usually confirmed with the clinical evaluation of the patient having a diagnostic splint or provisional prosthesis⁴.

This case report describes the prosthetic rehabilitation of a patient who had severely attrited maxillary anterior teeth with loss of all posterior teeth in mouth except the maxillary left molar with decreased vertical dimension.

Case Report

A 65-year-old male reported to the Department of Prosthodontics with a chief complaint of difficulty in chewing food and unpleasant appearance. The patient gave no significant medical history and did not report any signs of temporomandibular joint disorder or myofascial pain dysfunction.

Extra oral examination depicted no facial asymmetry or muscle tenderness. The facial type of the patient was square. A discrepancy between centric occlusion (CO) and maximum intercuspal position (MIP) was found when he had to be guided to a centric relation position with the bimanual technique.

Figure 1

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Intra oral examination revealed generalized attrited teeth seen in upper ant. region of the jaw due to loss of posterior support. The patient presented with an edge to edge bite due to habitual forward positioning of the mandible due to lack of occluding surfaces posteriorly [Figure 1]. Patient had undergone extraction of 14,15,16,25,26,27 a few years ago due to dental caries. Fixed dental prostheses were present in 35,36 region. [Figure 2a & 2b]

Figure 2a

Figure 2b

Radio graphic examination revealed that patient had undergone root canal treatment for 11,21,22,23, 6 months back due to severe attrition. [Figure 3a]

Figure 3

A diagnosis of decreased VDO was made based on the following findings^{1,3,5} -

1. Loss of posterior support: maxillary posterior teeth were missing, resulting in excessive wear of anterior teeth.
2. History of wear: Physiologic wear can be compensated by tooth eruption in general, but the accelerated wear may exceed the rate of eruption. The patient liked vegetables and acidic fruits. Patient gave history of the habit of clenching his teeth.
3. Inter occlusal rest space: The patient's inter occlusal rest space that was measured between nose tip and chin tip was

4-5 mm that was greater than the normal value 2 - 4 mm. The possible causes of patient's worn dentition that might include missing maxillary posterior teeth, para function, eating habit, and dental ignorance were explained to the patient and the patient was advised to go for RCT of 12,22,23,24.

For the maxillary anterior region, after completion of RCT of 12,13,14, post and core was planned followed by FDP of 11,12,13,14, 21,22,23. Patient was advised implant rehabilitation for missing posterior teeth. Due to his financial condition, he could not afford at present but he was motivated to place implants at a later stage. Hence, an interim maxillary denture was given to him. Patient was not willing for rehabilitation of mandibular arch as attrition was moderate. As there was clinical evaluation of reduced VDO, full mouth rehabilitation of maxillary arch with increased VDO was planned.

Procedure

1. Diagnostic impressions were made with irreversible hydro colloid poured with dental stone and diagnostic casts were made. [Figure 4a & 4b] [Figure 5a & 5b]

Figure 4a

Figure 4b

Figure 5a

Figure 5b

2. Facebow transfer of the maxillary cast was done and mounted on a semi adjustable articulator (Hanau, wide view articulator) and mandibular cast was mounted with the help of Lucia Jig in the anterior region and inter occlusal records in the posterior region [Figure 6a & 6b]. Vertical dimension was raised by 2 mm on the articulator.

Figure 6a

Figure 6b

3. A diagnostic wax-up of the worn out ant. maxillary teeth was carried out at the 2 mm increased vertical dimension

and teeth arrangement for an interim RPD for the missing post. teeth was done .[Figure 7]

Figure 7

4. Post space was prepared with the help of Peeso Reamers and the prefabricated posts were luted into the space and keeping the patient's ant guidance in mind ,the core build was done which was inclined labially.[Figure 8]

Figure 8

5. Tooth preparation was carried out. [Figure 9a,9b]

Figure 9a

Figure 9b

6. As the crown height was not satisfactory therefore, to increase the resistance & retention form, after preparation of 11 and 12 crown lengthening procedure was performed.[Figure 10]

Figure 10

7. The provisional fixed restorations were made from a putty index of the wax up and cemented with temporary cement (Free genol temporary pack; gc Corp., Tokyo, Japan), and the patient's adaptation was monitored [Figure 11] . A

posterior interim RPD was delivered to the patient.

Figure 11

8. Once the patient was adapted to the provisionals , a final full-arch impression for maxillary teeth was made using poly (vinyl siloxane) impression material and master casts were poured in die stone. This cast was mounted on a Hanau wide view articulator using the face bow transfer. [Figure 12a & 12b]

Figure 12a

Figure 12b

9. The wax pattern and core was fabricated on the maxillary cast and all the wax patterns were cast and metal copings were tried in the patients mouth with the RPD in place. A bite was taken with bite registration wax for the fabrication of new Interim RPD irt 16,17,24,25,26 . [Figure 13a & 13b]

Figure 13a

10. Definitive restorations with PFM crowns exhibiting a vital and natural appearance with proper contour and shade were fabricated. Permanent cementation was done with GIC type I luting cement . A new interim RPD for missing posterior teeth was adjusted and delivered. Oral hygiene instructions were given and follow-up was carried out at regular intervals. [Figure 14a & 14b]

Figure 14a

Figure 14b

Discussion

Tooth surfaces can undergo attrition, abrasion and erosion . There is a complex etiology to tooth attrition. There are few

clinical controlled trials available regarding restorative and prosthodontic techniques. The process of making clinical decisions can be complicated by a lack of information about the long-term clinical outcome of the treatment. Prior to taking any action, it is important to identify the cause of wear.

According to Turner and Missirlian, severely worn dentition treatment is classified based on the amount of the loss of VDO and space available to restore⁶. In this report, the patient was classified as category 3⁷. The three prerequisites for full mouth rehabilitation are healthy TMJ, anterior guidance harmony and non interfering posteriors⁸. These are interrelated and any disharmony between these will affect the stomatognathic system⁹. This patient presented with severe attrition of maxillary anterior teeth with missing posterior teeth. Patient showed loss of VD with limited available space. The treatment goal was to restore the worn out surfaces and replacement of missing tooth to enhance mastication and aesthetic appearance.

Decision-making full-mouth rehabilitation may be simultaneous restorations of full arch or segmental/sequential technique. However, each treatment has its pros and cons. Hence, treatment plan to be done in consideration of clinical condition and patient expectation and operators experience¹⁰. In this case, sequential steps of diagnosis, evaluation of loss of vertical dimension, increasing the vertical dimension, Post and core followed by preparation of teeth, provisionalization for one month at increased vertical dimension and finally definitive restorations was done.

Conclusion

In this clinical report, raising the vertical dimension of the occlusion, fixing a provisional restoration based on a precise diagnosis, and then using a metal ceramic fixed prosthesis and interim prosthesis for the definitive restoration demonstrated successful full mouth rehabilitation for severely worn-down dentition in the maxillary arch.

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